

RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT WITHIN THE HIGHER EDUCATION LANDSCAPE: A NARRATIVE LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Researcher Development, despite its significance, remains an under-examined area of research within higher education. This paper aims to provide an extensive and integrated overview of existing knowledge in this field, offering insights into key concepts and empirical findings. This narrative literature review critically explores various dimensions of Researcher Development. It also sheds light on the challenges that researchers commonly face in their careers. This review includes seven conceptual papers from 2005 to 2009 and 17 empirical papers published between 2000 and 2020. Three conceptual papers have contributed models or frameworks, enriching the understanding of the theoretical underpinnings of Researcher Development. The empirical literature reveals that Researcher Development unfolds through various phases and is contingent on the unique journey of each individual researcher. These distinct phases pose specific challenges, emphasizing the need for tailored and individualized support. Most of the studies concentrate on researchers with doctoral qualifications, underscoring a prevailing trend in the literature that neglects pre-doctoral researchers. This synthesis of existing knowledge serves to enhance the understanding of Researcher Development, acting as a valuable guide for educators, policymakers, and institutional leaders. It provides a comprehensive resource for those committed to advancing Researcher Development within higher education. The review notes the challenges encountered by researchers throughout their career paths, providing insights that can be utilized to enhance existing strategies and interventions in Researcher Development. The findings could serve as a foundation for shaping inclusive and effective strategies that can adapt to the evolving needs of researchers in the dynamic landscape of higher education.

Keywords: Keywords: Researcher Development, Higher Education, Literature Review

1 INTRODUCTION

This narrative literature review endeavours to navigate readers through an exploration of Researcher Development, encompassing an analysis of 24 scholarly articles spanning the period from 2000 to 2021. This corpus comprises seven conceptual papers and 17 empirical studies. The impetus behind this study stems from the author's engagement in Researcher Development within the higher education landscape, motivating a dedicated inquiry into the existing discourse.

The investigation unveiled a dearth in the scrutiny afforded to the domain of Researcher Development within the extant research literature. Moreover, the review unveiled pivotal interconnected concepts that necessitate concurrent consideration in the discourse on Researcher Development. Chief among these is

the nuanced characterization of the 'academic', the delineation of research careers, the intricacies of research leadership, and the influence of research culture. The investigation also unearthed challenges related to Researcher Development and the need for strategies and interventions to circumvent these challenges. It became evident that a holistic comprehension of Researcher Development is unattainable without cognizance of the multifaceted implications these concurrent concepts exert upon the overarching narrative.

To facilitate readability, this narrative literature review opts not to delineate between conceptual and empirical papers, instead comprehensively examining all articles as an integrated whole. This approach is adopted to furnish a cohesive and succinct comprehension of the literature under scrutiny.

2 HOW IS RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT EXAMINED IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION LANDSCAPE?

A diverse array of perspectives is applied in scrutinizing Researcher Development. Jenkins & Healey (2009), along with Kneale Edward-Jones, Walkington & Hill (2016), concentrate on Researcher Development in the context of undergraduate qualifications. Jenkins et al, (2009) advocate for a transformative overhaul of undergraduate curricula to intricately incorporate research, while Kneale et al., (2016) underscore the significance of providing undergraduates with opportunities for research engagement, notably through research conferences. Both studies posit that early involvement in research during undergraduate studies equips students with skillsets that enhance their employability and position them for success in their chosen careers.

Within the realm of higher education Researcher Development, a notable focus is directed towards doctoral students. Borders, Wester & Driscoll (2020) examine the Researcher Development of counselling doctoral students, emphasizing the relevance of contextual supports and barriers to the longitudinal development of doctoral students as researchers. Ait Saadi, Collins & Dash (2018) reflect on Researcher Development through the lens of a collaborative initiative in Malaysia, specifically the Borneo Research Education Conference series. Caskey, Stevens & Yeo (2020) delve into the development of doctoral students in education, aiming to describe and explain their development of a researcher identity. Disney, Harrowell, Mulhall & Ronayne (2013) explore the organisation of a conference by a small group of doctoral students and the consequential development and practice of a new skill set outside the usual research process. (Roulston, Preissle & Freeman (2013) explore the journeys of novice doctoral students in a qualitative research program, examining the developmental processes and challenges faced in selecting and developing research topics into dissertation studies.

Lee & Murray (2015) examine doctoral research from the supervisor's perspective, introducing a framework to enhance Researcher Development through a structured approach to supervising postgraduate students, particularly in academic writing. Albertyn, Collier-Peter & Morrison's (2018) study focuses on supporting supervisors and students during doctoral supervision, exploring the experience of research from both perspectives, and proposing a multi-level support framework for Researcher Development. Ward (2013) presents the results of a study into what is important in Researcher Development as perceived by doctoral students, their supervisors and research administrators (individuals who are responsible for managing the administrative processes related to postgraduate research).

The literature transitions from doctoral student development to the development of staff within higher education institutions. Gordon (2005) explores the development and management of research staff, with a particular focus on delving into the intricacies and complexities associated with the career life cycle of researchers. Mazmanian, Coe, Evans, Longo & Wright (2014) conducted a systematic review to determine the effectiveness of Researcher Development interventions in improving researcher behaviour in the clinical and translational science domain. Bray & Boon (2011) evaluated the use of the well-known Vitae framework, (Vitae, 2013), as a personal development planner for two cohorts of researchers who participated in a Researcher Development course. Gonzalez, Wester & Borders (2019) study was conducted with 49 assistant professors in counsellor education to learn about supports and barriers to Researcher Development in early career researchers. Murray & Cunningham (2011) investigate how a writer's retreat intervention can assist academics in meeting publication targets set by national bodies and institutions. O'Byrne (2011) investigates the emergence of a "researcher" dimension in the academic professional identities of lecturers operating in a teaching-focused institute. The purpose of Robbins & LePeau's (2018) constructivist instrumental case study of two pre-tenured faculty members examines how the process of writing and publishing from qualitative dissertations sparked Researcher Development. Debowski's (2006)

paper is based on an exploration of evaluations of Researcher Development needs and draws from multiple sources including an evaluation report of a Researcher Development program, a collaborative research project across six universities, and a workshop attended by academics and research managers.

Åkerlind (2008) deviates from the prevailing narrative by focusing on the individual researcher, investigating academics' ways of understanding their growth and development as university researchers and Borg (2001) utilizes his personal experience maintaining a research journal to exemplify the noteworthy impact that journal writing can have on enhancing researchers' comprehension of every aspect of the research process.

The scope of Researcher Development broadens to encompass the professional dimension. Evans (2011) proposes a holistic framework applicable across diverse professional settings, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach to Researcher Development. McCrystal's (2000) study extends this discourse to social workers, highlighting the continuity of research education and the unique needs of practitioners engaging in applied research. Nguyen (2012) extends Evans's work, highlighting the necessity for a conceptual framework in researching Researcher Development, integrating Vygotskian sociocultural and activity theories to emphasize the crucial role of sociocultural and contextual dimensions in this developmental process. Bromley & Warnock's (2021) conceptual paper examines the current 'state of the art' in the practice of the development of researchers, with a focus on doctoral students, early career researchers, and established professionals and they emphasize the need for more rigorous and robust research to provide evidence of good practice in the field of Researcher Development.

3 CONCEPTUALIZING KEY TERMS

3.1 The Academic

The author thought it important to highlight the multifaceted nature of the term "academic" within higher education. For this study, the term 'academic' will encompass undergraduates, doctoral students, postgraduate doctoral students, staff working in higher academia, and professionals involved with research. None of the articles examined explicitly define 'academic' but the implication is that an academic is working within the context of higher education and participating in research activity and scholarly pursuits. The overarching theme in these articles centres on the cultivation of individuals as researchers within academic or research-oriented environments. This narrative literature review specifically focuses on the research dimension of an academic role.

3.2 Defining the Research Career

The narrative has introduced the terms 'early career researchers' and 'career life cycle of researchers.' However, except for Debowski (2006), the scrutinized literature remains silent on precisely defining the nature of this research career. To furnish explicit definitions for these terminologies, the author has delved into additional scholarly works. The terms 'new' or 'novice' researchers conventionally denote individuals who have recently completed master's or doctoral studies (Darwin Holmes, 2020; Tomaszewski, Zaretsky & Gonzalez, 2020). These individuals are envisioned to ideally progress into the category of early career researchers, defined as those who have attained their doctoral degree or an equivalent qualification and are in the process of transitioning into independent researchers (Mason & Merga, 2021; Mtwisha, Jackson, Mitchel, Aikens, Kebirungi, Outtara & Viney, 2021; Mula, Rodriguez, Segovia & Cruz-Gonzales, 2021). Subsequently, early career researchers evolve into Mid-Career Researchers (MCRs); individuals with post-doctoral experience, including supervising doctoral candidates and recognized research output (Wong, 2019; Moran, Karlin, Lauchlan, Rappaport, Bleasdale, Wild & Dorr 2020). MCRs frequently take on the role of overseeing small research teams (Mtwisha et al., 2021), which by implication sees research leadership as the subsequent developmental phase. Debowski (2006) articulates four distinct phases of a research career: postgraduate internship, early-career researcher, mid-career researcher, and research leadership. Although the studies within this review may not explicitly define research careers, they allude to them through terms such as 'stages,' 'phases,' or characterize it as a 'process,' 'trajectory,' or 'journey'.

4 THE DYNAMIC NATURE OF RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT

Academics grow and develop throughout their research careers and this advancement in their capacity for research is generally referred to as "Researcher Development." This literature review acknowledges that this progression encompasses skills refinement, shifts in research attitudes, heightened proficiency in conducting research, subject matter enrichment, and an overall enhancement of research competence (Borders et al., 2020; Bromley & Warnock, 2021; Borg, 2001; Bray & Boon, 2011)

Albertyn et al. (2018) and Debowski (2006) emphasize that Researcher Development involves enhancing the quality of conducted research, while Lee & Murray's (2015) study outlines it as achieving successful completion of doctoral studies. Roulston et al. (2013) contextualize Researcher Development as doctoral students transitioning to proficient researchers.

Gordon (2005) emphasizes providing support to academics over their career cycle as a key aspect of Researcher Development. Mazmanian et al. (2014) elaborate on this notion of support by defining Researcher Development as a set of capacity-building activities designed to facilitate individual faculty members, teams of researchers, and central research administrations in acquiring skills that will aid in building relationships with the broader research community and developing and implementing strategies that increase institutional competitiveness. This is echoed by Ait Saadi et al. (2018) who envision Researcher Development as contributing to individual, institutional, and national goal attainment.

What does the above tell us about Researcher Development? It is a dynamic process involving various dimensions, and the perspectives outlined by different scholars contribute to a nuanced understanding of this concept. The emphasis is on continuous growth, skill acquisition, and strategic activities that contribute to individual and institutional success in the realm of research.

This is why the seminal work and definition by Evans (2011) is so profound. Evans is a highly cited author, and even in the context of this study, Mazmanian et al. (2014), Nguyen (2012), Robbins & LePeau (2018) and Bray & Boon (2011) all include her definition and note its contribution in their studies. Evans (2011) defines Researcher Development which is also inclusive of the different layers of Researcher Development coming through in the literature.

Researcher Development is described by Evans (2011, p. 82) as "the process whereby *people's* capacity and willingness to carry out the research components of their work or studies may be considered to be enhanced, with a degree of permanence that exceeds transitoriness". The term 'people' is used to be inclusive of all types of academics and a 'degree of permanence that exceeds transitoriness' emphasizes the lasting and sustained nature of the enhancements in individuals' capacity and willingness to carry out research activities. This implies that the changes and improvements resulting from Researcher Development are not fleeting or temporary but rather have a lasting impact on the individuals' abilities, attitudes, and approaches to research. This definition encapsulates the multi-layered nature of Researcher Development emerging in the literature, indicating that changes resulting from it are enduring and impactful, contributing to individuals' long-term growth and effectiveness as researchers.

The author asserts that Evans's (2011) definition of Researcher Development comprehensively considers all relevant studies, rendering it the most comprehensive interpretation. However, discerning what Researcher Development entails represents one facet, while probing how Researcher Development unfolds presents another dimension. This is where frameworks or conceptual models that underpin research development become pivotal, providing a foundational understanding of Researcher Development.

5 RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORKS

In support of her definition, Evans's (2011) conceptual model deconstructs Researcher Development into behavioural, attitudinal, and intellectual components, emphasizing the importance of physical activity (behavioural development) and mental activity (attitudinal and intellectual development) in enhancing Researcher Development. The emphasis lies on actively participating in research tasks and enhancing individuals' research-related behaviours to bolster overall research capacity (Evans, 2011). The attitudinal component involves the cultivation of attitudes, values, and beliefs that shape researchers' identities and inform their approaches to their work (Evans, 2011). This underscores the significance of addressing not only the technical facets of research but also the personal and psychological factors that impact individuals' involvement and effectiveness in research activities. The intellectual component of the model highlights the importance of fostering individuals' cognitive and analytical abilities to augment their research capacity. This emphasizes the value of addressing both the technical and intellectual dimensions of research in the Researcher Development process.

Jenkins & Healey's (2009) framework, designed for Researcher Development at the undergraduate level, aims to offer a comprehensive approach by integrating research experiences into the undergraduate curriculum. This involves fostering a research-informed culture, adapting assessment practices to incorporate research at both formative and summative levels, and implementing targeted, student-centric research interventions that support the development of students as researchers (Jenkins & Healey, 2009). Together, these components contribute to enhancing Researcher Development by providing students with

ongoing research experiences, skill development opportunities, and institutional support (Jenkins & Healey, 2009).

Albertyn et al. (2018) propose a multi-level Researcher Development framework that considers the perspectives of both doctoral students and their supervisors. The framework consists of three main factors influencing the completion of research: personal characteristics of the student, supervisory support, and institutional context.

Nguyen applies Evans' conceptual model of Researcher Development as a guideline for analysing qualitative data from existing Researcher Development literature and uses the model in conjunction with Vygotskian sociocultural and activity theory, Nguyen therefore provides a more nuanced understanding of the sociocultural and contextual dimensions of Researcher Development.

6 RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT – THE WHO

All the authors are clear about *who* is responsible for Researcher Development. It is a *shared responsibility* among all stakeholders engaged in the development of researchers. These encompass the academics (and the all-inclusive definition of the academic purported earlier), the academic institutions themselves, and the broader researcher community of research funders, relevant councils, and professional bodies. This underscores the collaborative nature of Researcher Development, where all stakeholders in some shape or form contribute to the growth and development of researchers.

7 RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT – THE HOW

Returning to Debowski's career cycle phases, the final developmental stage in the research career trajectory is research leadership, a crucial topic not yet addressed in the discourse. Existing literature emphasizes the institution's role and the significance of support, and within doctoral studies, supervisors already assume research leadership responsibilities. As academics progress in their research endeavours, effective research leadership becomes indispensable for guidance and support. Comprehensive Researcher Development initiatives should consider individual researcher characteristics, institutional support structures, and broader contextual factors influencing their growth. Thus, Researcher Development is intricately linked to research leadership and the overarching influence of research culture, as discussed in the framework section of this narrative, should both be integrated into the academic environment to foster holistic Researcher Development.

7.1 Research Leadership

The literature references the role of research leadership, addressing it through two primary lenses: Researcher Development, which centres on supporting research leaders in their career trajectory, and the role that research leaders play in the development of individual researchers. Gordon (2005) underscores the importance of cultivating research leaders, offering opportunities for leadership skill development, fostering interinstitutional collaborations, and enhancing capabilities in areas like writing and strategic research management. Bromley & Warnock (2021) identify success factors for research leaders, including holding a research doctorate, mentorship, conference attendance, postgraduate student supervision, active participation in research groups, assistance in grant applications, and financial support for initiating research careers. Jenkins & Healey (2009) emphasize the pivotal role research leaders play in shaping the research experiences of undergraduate students. Debowski's (2006) study underscores the importance of addressing the specific development needs of research leaders, focusing on leadership skills, strategic direction, mentorship, and sustained research excellence, advocating for tailored support and guidance to enhance the effectiveness of research leaders within the academic research community. Åkerlind (2008) highlights the necessity of providing support, recognition, and ongoing professional development opportunities for researchers at all career stages, including those in leadership roles.

Lee & Murray (2015) contend that effective research leadership at the supervisory level is indispensable for supporting the development of postgraduate researchers, a sentiment echoed by Albertyn et al. (2018), who recognize the significance of supervisor support in the postgraduate supervision relationship and the role of supervisors as influencers of students' research experiences. Murray & Cunningham (2011) delve into research leaders and leadership, emphasizing institutional support and strategic investment in nurturing the professional development of emerging researchers within higher education. While Roulston et al. (2013) study does not explicitly address research leaders or leadership, it indirectly touches upon the role of doctoral supervisors, advisors, and committee members in guiding and supporting doctoral students through the research process. Evans (2011) advocates for a comprehensive approach to Researcher Development,

encompassing not only the enhancement of research skills but also the transformation of individuals into effective research leaders.

The literature underscores a nuanced understanding of the symbiotic relationship between Researcher Development and research leadership, emphasizing mentorship, institutional support, and the multifaceted roles of research leaders in shaping the academic landscape. Varying perspectives contribute to the definition of Research Leadership, with common themes including supporting other researchers and influencing researchers' behaviour. The academic environment housing these individual researchers and research leaders cannot progress without a supportive research culture.

7.2 Research Culture

Although not explicitly investigated by the authors, the pivotal role of the institution and the research culture in fostering Researcher Development was not overlooked. Gordon (2005), Bromley & Warnock (2021) and (Lee & Murray, 2015) underscore the significance of a supportive research culture in advancing the career development of researchers. Evans (2011) in a broader context of Researcher Development, highlights the importance of comprehending and navigating the research culture within academic and professional settings, acknowledging its substantial role in shaping individuals' attitudes, behaviours, and professional growth engaged in research activities. Nguyen (2012) stresses the necessity of enriching the knowledge base concerning the development of research cultures and the processes by which researchers evolve within the research context.

Borders et al. (2020) identify a supportive research culture as a crucial factor in enhancing doctoral students' readiness for research roles, recognizing that its impact can vary within institutions, necessitating tailored research instruction and experiences based on researchers' needs. Mazmanian et al. (2014) underscores the recognition of the importance of research culture and the imperative for broader engagement in discussions related to Researcher Development and the cultivation of a robust research culture. Åkerlind (2008) emphasizes the need for a nuanced understanding of individual perspectives and experiences in shaping the broader research culture.

Bray & Boon (2011) address research culture by emphasizing the need for comprehensive changes in policy and practice regarding developmental opportunities and support for career researchers within higher education institutions. Debowski (2006) deems research culture as a critical factor in supporting Researcher Development and enhancing research productivity and quality, emphasizing the importance of a supportive and nurturing research culture that recognizes and addresses the diverse needs and challenges faced by researchers at different career stages. The study advocates for tailored support and guidance to enhance the capabilities and effectiveness of researchers within the academic research community. Kneale et al. (2016) suggest that undergraduate research conferences can shape the research culture by providing a supportive and encouraging environment for young researchers. Although Gonzalez et al. (2019) do not explicitly define or address research culture, they discuss contextual supports and barriers to new faculty Researcher Development, including mentoring relationships, collaboration around research, and institutional and departmental policies and practices supporting research productivity.

McCrystal's (2000) study aims to cultivate a research culture within the social work profession by equipping practitioners with the skills and knowledge to engage in research and promoting closer relationships between research and practice. Roulston et al. (2013) highlight the influence of research culture on the development of new scholars and how doctoral students integrate their research interests with the broader academic and disciplinary contexts. While (Ward, 2013) does not explicitly address research culture, the author provides insights into the support and administrative processes contributing to the success of the researcher's development journey, impacting the broader research culture within academic institutions and research organizations. O'Byrne's (2011) study underscores the need for supportive structures and cultures to foster the development of researcher identities within teaching-focused higher education institutions.

The provided text emphasizes the crucial role of the institution and research culture in nurturing Researcher Development.

8 RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT CHALLENGES

Given the varying nature of the studies, it becomes evident that varying definitions of Researcher Development provide challenges for the individual researcher, the institution, and the broader research community.

8.1 Diverse Perspectives on Research Career Phases

The literature highlights an insufficient exploration of various phases in the research career. Gordon (2005) asserts that the complexity of the research career life cycle is overlooked, as traditional career models do not align with the dynamic nature of research fields. This sentiment is echoed by Bray & Boon (2011) and Robbins & LePeau (2018), emphasizing the necessity for tailored support methods in academia due to the unique challenges faced by university researchers. (Evans (2011) notes a limited focus on early-career stage development, neglecting the ongoing development of academics within the university environment. Kneale et al. (2016) underscores the need to address varying perspectives on research, requiring tailored support for researchers at different career stages. Debowski (2006) identifies a lack of recognition for career phases, emphasizing the predominant focus on early-career Researcher Development.

8.2 Challenges for Individual Researchers

Åkerlind (2008) highlights the challenge of varying views and experiences among academics in their research development. Lee & Murray (2015) note individual researchers' struggles with writing-related anxieties, conceptual thinking, structuring writing, and submitting written work. Borders et al. (2020) identify challenges related to self-efficacy, research competencies, knowledge, and experiences. Albertyn et al. (2018) and Borg, (2001) highlight challenges faced by doctoral students, including a primary interest in theoretical and practical knowledge rather than research, a lack of research skills, and difficulties expressing creative thinking. Debowski (2006) highlights time management challenges. Gonzalez et al. (2019) point to internal challenges such as negative emotional states and problems with work/life balance. Murray & Cunningham (2011) emphasize the pressure on researchers to publish and become independent researchers, while Roulston et al. (2013) discuss challenges faced by novice researchers, including integrating personal research interests with disciplinary fields and navigating scholarly debates.

8.3 Limited Evidence of Effective Developmental Interventions

Persistent challenges exist concerning developmental interventions instituted by institutions. (Bromley & Warnock (2021). highlight limited evidence of the efficacy of developmental interventions, especially for post-doctorates transitioning into various careers. (Mazmanian et al.2014) note the scarcity of evidence supporting the effectiveness of Researcher Development interventions. Gordon (2005) emphasizes the need for clear policies, practices, and resource allocation for effective implementation of interventions. Debowski (2006) identifies a lack of comprehensive Researcher Development strategies in many universities, attributing this to factors such as minimal understanding, fragmented responsibility, and a lack of support for Researcher Development programs.

8.4 Challenges in Research Leadership

Nguyen (2012) highlights an inadequate understanding of how various constituencies, including research leaders, develop within the research context. Debowski (2006) emphasizes the need to address the needs of advanced researchers and research leaders, recognizing the challenge of fulfilling strategic, mentoring, and research excellence roles effectively.

8.5 Challenges in Research Culture

The writers note challenges related to research cultures. Gordon (2005) highlights the impact of evolving research cultures characterised by the rapid dissemination of knowledge, global growth of the research community, changes in legislation, and societal expectations. Åkerlind (2008) calls for a research culture accommodating diverse experiences of Researcher Development. Murray & Cunningham (2011) stress the importance of research culture and the challenges associated with it, emphasizing the need for effective supervision and a framework for doctoral writing. McCrystal (2000) indicates a need for practitioners to understand and adapt to the research culture and environment for successful role transitions from professional to researcher.

8.6 Government, Funding Bodies, and the Broader Research Community

Mazmanian et al. (2014) note a lack of guidance from the government and limited engagement by academics and managers of higher education institutions in global discussions on Researcher Development. Gordon (2005) underscores the impact of shifting priorities and expectations from governments and funding bodies on required skills, competitive opportunities, and the perceived quality of research.

8.7 Skills Development Challenges

Kneale et al. (2016) and Disney et al. (2013) highlight a lack of skills development at the undergraduate and doctoral levels respectively, and Ward (2013) calls for formalizing and structuring skills development for postgraduate students. Ward (2013) emphasizes the challenges of transitioning to professional researchers and preparing postgraduate researchers for employment marketplace demands. Bromley & Warnock (2021) notes neglect of graduate student research skill development.

8.8 Lack of Conceptual Clarity

Nguyen (2012) notes limited empirical research beyond doctoral students and a scarcity of research on the development of researchers beyond the doctoral level. Evans (2011) and Nguyen (2012) both highlight the absence of a clear definition of Researcher Development contributing to conceptual confusion.

9 RESEARCHER DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES AND INTERVENTIONS

The discussion below encompasses various aspects such as mentorship, building research networks, skills development, training, the institutional context, tools for development, the role of research leaders, collaboration, broadening the focus, theoretical frameworks, personal factors, and the importance of tailored and holistic approaches.

9.1 Development at All Career Stages

The authors collectively argue that development initiatives should span all stages of a researcher's career, beginning from undergraduate levels to doctoral students and beyond. They emphasize the need for a continuous, lifelong approach to Researcher Development, recognizing that each stage presents unique challenges and opportunities.

9.2 Mentorship

Bromley & Warnock (2021), Mazmanian et al. (2014), Debowski (2006), Gonzalez et al. (2019) and Robbins & LePeau (2018) underscore the pivotal role of mentorship in Researcher Development. They stress the importance of effective mentorship programs, highlighting how mentorship provides guidance, support, and networking opportunities, particularly for early-career researchers and research leaders.

9.3 Building Research Networks and Collaborations

Gordon (2005), Bromley & Warnock (2021), Debowski (2006), McCrystal (2000), and Gonzalez et al. (2019) emphasize the creation of collaborative research networks. These networks are seen as crucial for fostering research impact and encouraging partnerships with community stakeholders, industry, and professional associates, thereby enriching the research environment.

9.4 Skills Development

Lee & Murray (2015), Robbins & LePeau (2018), Gordon (2005), Disney et al. (2013) and (Ward (2013) highlight the need for a diverse set of skills provided by the relevant institutions. This includes practical skills, writing strategies, and transferable skills such as project management and communication, ensuring that researchers are well-equipped for a variety of roles in their careers.

9.5 Training

Bromley & Warnock (2021), Evans 2011), Kneale et al. (2016), (McCrystal,2000) and Ward (2013) emphasize the importance of structured training. This encompasses research integrity, leadership skills, and the formalization of skills development. The goal is to provide researchers with comprehensive training opportunities to navigate the complexities of their nuanced roles.

9.6 Research Culture/Environment/Institutional Context

Gordon (2005), Nguyen (2012), Gonzalez et al. (2019), O'Byrne (2011) and (Ward (2013) highlight the role of the institutional context in Researcher Development. They stress the creation of supportive, inclusive environments and the mainstreaming of developmental initiatives. An institutional culture that values research is deemed crucial.

9.7 Tools for Development

Bromley & Warnock (2021), Borg (2001), Murray & Cunningham (2011), (Kneale et al. (2016) and Roulston et al. (2013) focus on practical tools and interventions. These include reflective journaling, research journals, writers' retreats, and other writing strategies. Such tools aim to facilitate and enhance the researcher's development process.

9.8 Role of Research Leaders

Borders et al. (2020) and Debowski (2006) emphasize the critical role of research leaders in shaping the next generation of researchers. They advocate for leadership development programs to address challenges faced by research leaders, thereby contributing to the overall growth of the research community.

9.9 Collaboration

Evans (2011), Caskey et al. (2020), Gonzalez et al. (2019) and O'Byrne (2011) highlight the importance of collaboration. Initiatives that encourage collaboration and networking are seen as essential for Researcher Development, fostering positive role models, and creating opportunities for shared learning experiences.

9.10 Widening the Focus of Researcher Development

Evans (2011), Nguyen (2012), Ait Saadi et al. (2018) and Albertyn et al. (2018) suggest broadening the focus of Researcher Development beyond technical skills. They underscore the impact of research culture, institutional norms, and values on the professional and intellectual growth of researchers.

9.11 Theoretical Model

Evans (2011), Lee & Murray (2015), Nguyen (2012) and Bray & Boon (2011) call for the development of theoretical frameworks to guide Researcher Development. These frameworks provide structured approaches that inform both research and practice, offering a foundation for systematic growth.

9.12 Personal/Self-efficacy

Evans (2011), Åkerlind (2008), Ait Saadi et al. (2018), Albertyn et al. (2018), Gonzalez et al. (2019), O'Byrne (2011) and Robbins & LePeau (2018) focus on personal factors influencing Researcher Development. This includes personal motivations, self-efficacy, resilience, and the importance of practising self-advocacy for continued professional and personal growth.

9.13 Individualized Interventions

Ait Saadi et al. (2018), Debowski (2006), Åkerlind (2008) and Bray & Boon (2011) stress the need for tailored development programs. Recognizing diverse needs and career stages, individualized approaches to Researcher Development are deemed important for addressing unique requirements.

9.14 Developmental and Holistic Approach

Robbins & LePeau (2018) emphasize a developmental approach to graduate and postdoctoral education which involves mentoring and preparing students for future careers by recognizing that a holistic developmental approach is essential for long-term success. This includes researcher identity development and partnering with students in constructing educational experiences that facilitate overall growth, acknowledging the multifaceted nature of Researcher Development. Bromley & Warnock (2021) suggest the importance of longer cohort-based activities over short workshops, emphasizing sustained and comprehensive Researcher Development efforts. This approach aims to provide ongoing support and learning opportunities for researchers.

The discourse on Researcher Development encapsulates a unanimous call for a continuous, lifelong commitment to fostering growth and skills enhancement. Acknowledging the distinct challenges and opportunities encountered at various career stages, the authors advocate for a holistic approach that spans from undergraduate levels to postdoctoral and beyond.

10 DISCUSSION

Out of the 24 articles under scrutiny, 7 are conceptual frameworks, and 17 are empirical studies. Notably, only one paper, authored by Mazmanian, underwent examination within the context of private higher education. While this study does not specifically delve into this aspect, it merits acknowledgement,

particularly considering the global expansion of private higher education (Bjarnason, Cheng, Fielden, Lemaitre, Levy and Varghese, 2009). It is logical to anticipate that Researcher Development within these institutions warrants scrutiny as well. Worth noting is that Mazmanian et al. (2014) study was conducted in Vietnam. The remaining 26 studies exclusively pertain to public higher education, with a concentration on research-intensive universities in Ireland, the United Kingdom, the United States, and Australia. Albertyn et al. (2018) study was conducted in South Africa. This highlights a biased focus on Western countries, underscoring the need to address Researcher Development in a more globally inclusive manner.

Existing literature underscores the imperative for a comprehensive understanding of the researcher's career and its correlation with Researcher Development. Without this understanding, interventions are likely to continue to be ineffective. As the scope of Researcher Development broadens to encompass the private sector and diverse academic roles, conceptual clarity becomes crucial. Evans's (2011) work facilitates this conceptualization, and, as she suggests, its application in various contexts will enhance its theoretical foundations, providing stakeholders with a valuable tool for guiding Researcher Development initiatives.

It's noteworthy that these studies cover more than two decades, yet the identical challenges endure. This suggests that the higher education landscape has not evolved as necessary. Interventions remain problematic, and both research leadership and research culture still lack the requisite structure to effectively enhance Researcher Development.

The author posits that a significant gap in this narrative lies in determining 'how' to identify the inherent developmental needs at the individual research level, irrespective of their academic roles. Identifying these needs is essential for crafting tailored interventions. While this may seem like a daunting task, with proper institutional support, a positive research culture, empowered research leaders, and policies offering clear directives, authentic, individualised interventions can be crafted. This is what future research in the realm of Researcher Development should focus on. The frameworks provide structure, but how does institutional leadership, through their research leaders, 'meet an academic where he or she is at', academically and personally? This is not an easy question to answer, but without going down to the granular level of the needs of the individual academic, interventions will continue to be ineffective, and challenges as highlighted in the literature will persist.

11 CONCLUSION

Examining the under-explored realm of Researcher Development, especially within the higher education landscape, is crucial. This entails placing increased emphasis on the collective responsibility for Researcher Development and advocating for the establishment of frameworks that facilitate collaboration among stakeholders. Evans' seminal work is lauded for its role in acknowledging and articulating the intricate involvement of diverse stakeholders in Researcher Development. Recognizing the shared responsibility underscores the need for a concerted and coordinated endeavour that encompasses not only individual researchers but also involves academic institutions, mentors, supervisors, and policymakers. It is imperative to differentiate between various research career phases when conceiving and executing Researcher Development initiatives. A one-size-fits-all approach is deemed inadequate, necessitating tailored strategies and interventions that cater to the unique needs and challenges encountered by researchers at different career stages. Research leadership and research culture emerge as critical areas warranting in-depth exploration due to their profound impact on Researcher Development. Integral to comprehensive strategies and interventions endorsed by relevant stakeholders is the understanding and enhancement of research leadership skills, along with the cultivation of a positive research culture. The dynamic nature of academia, exemplified by the expanding definition of academic roles, adds an element of excitement to this research domain. Consequently, Researcher Development emerges as a dynamic field demanding nuanced consideration, collaborative endeavours, and customized strategies to effectively address the evolving requirements of researchers within the higher education context.

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